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GLUTEN-FREE BREAD ENRICHED WITH NON-GERMINATED AND GERMINATED ALFALFA SEED FLOUR: ASSESSMENT OF NUTRIENT CONTENT IN RELATION TO COMMERCIAL COUNTERPARTS

Marijana Djordjević*, Miljana Djordjević, Zorica Tomičić, Elizabet Janić Hajnal, Biljana Cvetković, Miona Belović, Jelena Filipović

Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Bulevar cara Lazara 1, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia

*Corresponding author:

E-mail address: marijana.djordjevic@fins.uns.ac.rs

Considering that 1–2% of the human population worldwide lives with diagnosed coeliac disease which requires a lifelong adherence to a gluten-free (GF) diet, the research community effort to develop a new range of quality GF products has increased in the last decade. Although advances regarding the technological and sensory quality of GF bakery products were partially achieved, severe drawbacks in terms of nutrient deficiencies (lack of proteins, vitamins, fibres, antioxidants, and minerals) still represent a challenge to combat. Legumes emerge as a compelling strategy to combat nutrient deficiency in GF bread (GFB) and enable shifting towards a more sustainable diet due to their high protein content and low environmental impact. Considering the presented background, this study aimed to explore the effect of non-germinated and germinated alfalfa seed flour addition (5% on maize flour/starch basis) on GFB nutrient (protein, ash, lipid, carbohydrates content and energetic value) and mineral content (Ca, Mg, Fe, Zn), and compare it with control (without alfalfa) and commercial GFB available on the market. A higher content of protein, ash, and lipid was observed in GFB containing alfalfa compared to control and commercial GFB. Conversely, alfalfa-enriched GFBs were characterised by lower carbohydrate content (30.1–31.7 g/100 g) and energetic value ranging from 874 to 894 KJ. As regards to mineral content, a significant increase in Mg (from 342.2 to 908.3 mg/kg), and K (from 968.8 to 1478.9 mg/kg) was observed in alfalfa-enriched GFB, while lower content of Ca (320.0–462.8 mg/kg) and Fe (10.2–10.3 mg/kg) was recorded compared to commercial GFB (33.8 mg/kg). However, Fe content in alfalfa-enriched GFB was still higher than in control GFB (6.6 mg/kg). Significant differences in nutrient and mineral content were not observed between GFBs containing non-germinated and germinated alfalfa seed flour suggesting that both flours of this legume can be used as ingredients for improving nutrient content in GFB.

Keywords: gluten-free, bread, alfalfa, germination, nutrients

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